

Isocoumarins: Part III. Preparation and Cyclisation of 2-Carboxy-3, 6-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde

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Oxidation of 2-hydroxy-4, 7-dimethoxyindan-1-one by periodic acid furnished 2-carboxy-3, 6-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde which was cyclised with *ortho* phosphoric acid to 5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin.

A general route to isocoumarin synthesis¹ was developed by us which involved the preparation of 2-hydroxyindan-1-ones, their oxidation with periodic acid and cyclisation of the resulting 2-Carboxyphenyl-acetaldehydes. Following this reaction sequence, 5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IV) has now been synthesised.

The starting material, 2,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (Id) required for our work, has been prepared earlier² in 70% yield from quinol dimethyl ether by the application of the modified Gattermann synthesis. We, however, secured the aldehyde (Id) in 72% yield from methyl 2,5-dimethoxybenzoate³ (Ia) by the McFadyen-Stevens reaction⁴. The aldehyde (Id), on Doebner reaction with malonic acid in pyridine containing piperidine, gave 2, 5-dimethoxycinnamic acid⁵ (Ic) which was reduced with sodium amalgam to β -(2,5-dimethoxyphenyl) propionic acid⁶ (If). The latter was also obtained alternatively by malonic ester synthesis. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the ester (Ia) followed by treatment of the resulting alcohol³ (Ig) with hydrogen bromide yielded 2,5-dimethoxybenzyl bromide⁷ (Ih). Interaction of Ih with the carbanion of ethyl malonate, followed by hydrolysis furnished the malonic acid derivative which, on being heated, afforded the propionic acid (If). Cyclisation of If with PPA gave 4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one⁸ (IIa) in 94.5% yield. It was next converted into 2-oximino-4,7

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| (a) : R = COOCH ₃ | (a) : R = H |
| (b) : R = CONHNH ₂ | (b) : R = NOH |
| (c) : R = CONHNH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ -(<i>p</i>) | (c) : R = N ₂ |
| (d) : R = CHO | (d) : R = OAC |
| (e) : R = CH-CHCOOH | (e) : R = Br |
| (f) : R = CH ₂ .CH ₂ .COOH | (f) : R = OH |
| (g) : R = CH ₂ OH | |
| (h) : R = CH ₂ Br | |

(III)

(IV)

dimethoxyindan-1-one⁹ (IIb) with isoamyl nitrite and hydrochloric acid. The sodium salt of IIb when reacted with ammonia and sodium hypochlorite provided 2-diazo-4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIc) in 92% yield, which with glacial acetic acid led to 2-acetoxy-4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IId) in 91% yield. It was also obtained by an alternative route. 2-Bromo-4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIe), prepared by the action of cupric bromide on the indanone (IIa), was treated with sodium acetate in hot dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) to afford the acetoxy derivate (IId) in 66.6% yield. We had earlier reported¹ that acetolysis of 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one did not prove satisfactory since with potassium acetate in refluxing glacial acetic acid only a maximum 10% yield of 2-acetoxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one was obtained. Later it has been observed¹⁰ that acetolysis readily takes place in DMSO as solvent, providing a facile route to the preparation of 2-acetoxy derivatives of 5,6-dimethoxy-, 4,5-dimethoxy-, and 5-methoxyindan-1-ones in good yields from the corresponding 2-bromoindan-1-ones. Saponification of the acetoxy derivative (IId) with refluxing aqueous potassium carbonate furnished 2-hydroxy-4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIf). In contrast to our previous observation¹ the deacetylation did not take place when the hydrolysis was carried out at 0°. The ketol (IIf) was oxidised with periodic acid to yield 2-carboxy-3,6-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (III) which, on cyclisation with *ortho* phosphoric acid furnished 5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin in 97% yield. This isocoumarin has been earlier⁹ prepared by the application of Dickmann-Meiser method.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s and b.p.s are uncorrected. PPA used was of B.D.H. Reagent grade. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°. All organic extracts were dried with Na₂SO₄.

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Methyl 2,5-dimethoxybenzoate (Ia). Dimethyl sulphate (36.5 ml) and 25% aq. NaOH (36 ml) was added alternately to a well stirred solution of 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (25 g; Eastman grade) in 10% aq. NaOH so that there was a considerable rise of temperature. The solution was boiled for an hour, cooled and acidified. The solid that precipitated was filtered and crystallised from water to give 2,5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (25 g.), m.p. 77° (lit.,¹¹ m.p. 78-79.5°). Esterification of the acid (50 g.) with methanol (250 ml.) and conc. H₂SO₄ (10 ml.) in the usual way yielded Ia (45 g.; 84%), b.p. 124-26°/2mm. (lit.,³ b.p. 95.8°/1 mm.).

2,5-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde (Id). Ia (10 g.) and 80% hydrazine hydrate (10 ml.) in ethanol (25 ml.) were refluxed for 2.5 hr., most of the solvent distilled off and the residue poured into water. The aq. solution was saturated with NaCl and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 30 ml.). Evaporation of the solvent gave pure Ib as colourless needles (9.5 g.; 95%), m.p. 92-3° (lit.,¹² yield, 66.6%; m.p. 92°). A mixture of Ib (9.5 g.) and tosyl chloride (10 g.) in anhydrous pyridine (10 ml.) was heated on water bath for 1.5 hr. and poured into crushed ice when a granular light brown solid separated. It was filtered, washed with dil. HCl and water. Crystallisation from ethanol afforded Ic as colorless prismatic needles (16 g., 98.4%), m.p. 162-63° (decomp.) (Found: C, 54.6; H, 5.3. C₁₆H₁₈O₅N₂S requires C, 54.8; H, 5.1%). Ic (8 g.) suspended in ethylene glycol (55 ml.) as heated to 155-60° (bath temp.) and treated, in one portion, with anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (8 g.). The mixture was kept at 160° for 3 min., allowed to cool somewhat, and diluted with water (250 ml.) when a brown solid precipitated. It was collected, washed with water and dried in an exiccator to give 2,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (3 g.), m.p. 49-50° (lit.,¹³ m.p. 53°). The filtrate on extraction with ether gave a further crop (0.1 g.). Total yield : 3.1 g.; 88%.

2,5-Dimethoxybenzyl alcohol (Ig). Following the lit. procedure³, reduction of Ia (21g.) with LiAlH₄ (2.3 g.) in dry ether (300 ml.) gave Ig (16 g.; 89.6%), b.p. 119-22°/0.8 mm. (lit.³, b.p. 122-25°/1 mm.).

β-(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl) propionic acid (If). *Method* (a): 2,5-Dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (Id; 9 g.), malonic acid (11.7 g.), anhydrous pyridine (25 ml.) and piperidine (0.5 ml.) were refluxed for 3 hr., cooled and poured into ice water acidified with conc. HCl. The resulting precipitate was collected, washed with water and crystallised from isopropanol to afford 2,5-dimethoxycinnamic acid (10 g.; 92.5%), m.p. 147-48° (lit.,⁵ m.p. 147°; yield 95%). The cinnamic acid (Ie; 10 g.) was reduced with 3% Na-Hg (400 g.) in faintly acidic solution according to lit. method⁶ to furnish If in almost quantitative yield. It was distilled *in vacuo* at 155-60° (bath temp.)/2 mm. to afford colourless oil which solidified. Crystallisation from ether-light petroleum gave pure If as long needles (8.5 g.; 85%), m.p. 65-6° (lit.⁸, m.p. 65-6°).

Method (b). The reported method⁷ was modified by using HBr instead of PBr₃; 2,5-dimethoxybenzyl alcohol (Ig; 10 g.) in anhydrous benzene (54 ml.) was saturated with dry HBr and then poured into ice water with vigorous stirring. The benzene layer was collected and the aq. solution was extracted with benzene (3 × 20 ml.). The combined benzene extracts was successively washed with aq. NaHCO₃, water and dried. Concen-

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tration of the solution to a small bulk provided pure 2,5-dimethoxy benzyl bromide (Ih) as colourless needles (13.6 g.; 99%), m.p. 75-6° (lit.,⁷ m.p. 75-6°; yield 85%). The bromomethyl compound (Ih; 20 g.) in absolute ethanol (85 ml.), was added dropwise, with stirring, to ethyl sodiomalonate, prepared by the gradual addition of ethyl malonate (32.7 g.), to sodium (2.9 g.), in absolute ethanol (65 ml.) The mixture was stirred for 10 hr. at room temperature and finally refluxed for 1.5 hr. It was concentrated to a small volume under reduced pressure. The residue was refluxed with NaOH (16.2 g.) in water (60 ml.) for 3 hr. The mixture was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residual alkaline solution was washed with ether and then acidified with 5N HCl. The resulting precipitate was crystallised from ethyl acetate to give α -carboxy- β -(2,5-dimethoxyphenyl) propionic acid, m.p. 161-62° (decomp.). It was gradually heated during 1 hr., from 150° to 190° (bath temp.) to yield crude If which was purified by distillation and subsequent crystallisation as in method (a). Yield 16g.; 88.4%; m.p. and mixed m.p. 65-6°.

4,7-Dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIa). The reported method⁸ was modified by using PPA instead of P₂O₅ in benzene: The foregoing propionic acid (If; 10 g.) was added, in one lot, with stirring to PPA (120 g.) at 55°. The temperature was then gradually raised to 65°, which was maintained for 15 min. It was poured into ice water, pH of the solution adjusted to 6 by the addition of aq. NaOH and the light brown precipitate that separated was filtered. An additional crop was isolated by extracting the filtrate with ethyl acetate. The combined crude product was purified by chromatography of its benzene solution over Brockmann's alumina, followed by crystallisation from isopropanol. Pure IIa was isolated as colourless needles (8.6 g.; 94.5%), m.p. 124-25° (lit.,⁸ m.p. 124.5-25.5°; yield 82.4%).

4,7-Dimethoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one (IIb). The reported method⁹ was modified as follows: Isoamyl nitrite (3.2 ml.) was added to a stirred solution of (IIa; 9.5 g.) in methyl cellosolve (40 ml.) and HCl (12.5 ml., conc.) when a solid began to separate within a min. An additional quantity of isoamyl nitrite (3.2 ml.) was added and the mixture was stirred for 1 hr. The resulting crystalline slurry was poured into cold water, the solid filtered, washed well with water and dilute ethanol. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished pure IIb as silky pale yellow needles (9 g.; 86.5%), m.p. 237-38° (decomp.) (lit.⁹, m.p. 237-38° (decomp.), yield 63.6%).

2-Diazo-4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIc). A solution of IIb (1.36 g.) in aq. NaOH (0.32N; 20 ml.) was stirred and cooled to -2°, when after 5 min a portion of the sodium salt separated. 15N. NH₄OH (0.5 ml.) was added, followed by dropwise addition of NaOCl solution (5.36%; 20 ml.) during 10 min., the temperature being maintained throughout at -2°. The reaction mixture was held at this temperature for 1 hr. after the addition was complete. The ice bath was then removed and stirring continued when the diazo compound separated at 3°. It was stirred for further 2 hr. when the reaction mixture gradually attained the room temperature (33°). The product was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. It weighed 1.2 g. (92.3%), m.p. 154-55° (decomp.), and was used for the next step without further purification. A sample crystallised from ethyl acetate furnished a specimen of pure IIc as yellow needles, m.p. 155-56° (decomp.). (Found: C, 60.6; H, 4.3; N, 12.7. C₁₁H₁₀O₃N₂ requires C, 60.5; H, 4.5; N, 12.8%).

2-Bromo-4, 7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIe). A solution of IIa in methanol (12 ml.) was treated with a solution of cupric bromide (4.9 g.) and KBr (1.5 g.) in water (6 ml.) and refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. It was cooled, diluted with water (100 ml.) and the

resulting solid was filtered. It was extracted with chloroform, the extract washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent left a solid residue which was crystallised from isopropanol to afford pure IIe as pale yellow needles (1.7 g.; 60.7%), m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 48.6; H, 3.9. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3Br$ requires C, 48.7; H, 4.05%).

2-Acetoxy-4,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIId). *Method* (a) To the diazoketone (IIc; 1 g.) glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) was added gradually when N_2 evolved copiously and a clear solution was obtained. After 2 hr., it was diluted with water (50 ml.) and extracted with benzene (3×10 ml.). The extract was washed with aq. sodium bicarbonate, water and dried. The benzene solution was concentrated and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann's alumina, using the same solvent as eluent. The elute on evaporation gave a colourless solid, which on crystallisation from boiling water yielded pure IIId as colourless needles (1 g.; 91%), m.p. 132-33°. (Found: C, 62.3; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6%). It reduced hot Fehling's solution.

Its 2,4-DNP, was crystallised from dioxan as orange needles, m.p. 257-58° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.30. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.02%).

Method (b) A mixture of the bromoindan-1-one (IIe; 1.7 g.) and fused sodium acetate (1.2 g.) in dimethyl sulfoxide (30 ml.) was heated on water bath for 1.5 hr. and poured into water. The aq. solution was extracted with benzene and worked up as in method (a) to yield IIId (1.0 g.; 66.6%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 132-33°.

2-Hydroxy-4, 7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (IIIf). A mixture of IIId (2 g.) K_2CO_3 (1.4 g.) and water (50 ml.) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. The mixture was diluted with water (100 ml.) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×15 ml.). Evaporation of the solvent left a residue which was crystallised from ethyl acetate as pale yellow needles (1.5 g.; 90.3%), m.p. 139-40°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 5.5. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.7%). It readily reduced Fehling's solution in cold and formed a blue precipitate with baryta, a characteristic test¹⁴ for cyclic ketols.

Its 2,4-DNP was crystallised from dioxan as red needles, m.p. 238-39° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.6. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.4%).

2-Carboxy-3,6-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (III). A solution of HIO_4 (0.73 g.) in water (8.4 ml.) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of (IIIf; 0.8 g.) in methyl cellosolve (35 ml.) at 0°. After the addition was complete, the ice bath was removed and the mixture was held at room temperature (33°) for 2 hr. It was diluted with water (50 ml.) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×10 ml.). The combined extract was repeatedly washed with aq. sodium bicarbonate; the alkaline washings were combined, cooled (0°), and acidified with dil. HCl when III separated as colourless needles (0.5 g.; 78.1%, based on recovery of the starting material), m.p. 157-58°. A sample crystallised from ethyl acetate afforded pure III, m.p. 159-60°. (Found: C, 58.3; H, 5.7. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.9; H, 5.3%).

5,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (IV). A mixture of (IIIb; 0.5 g.) and H_3PO_4 (d, 1.75; 2 ml.) was heated at 130-35° (bath temp.) for 20 min. when a clear brown solution resulted. It was poured on ice, extracted with benzene (3×10 ml.), the extract washed with

aq. sodium bicarbonate, water, and dried. The solution was concentrated and percolated through a column of Brockmann's alumina, using benzene as eluent. The eluate was concentrated to a small volume, diluted with a little light petroleum and kept in a refrigerator to furnish IV as colourless needles (0.44 g. ; 97.7%), m.p. 96-8°. Several recrystallisations from benzene-light petroleum raised the melting point to 105.6° (lit.,⁹ m.p. 102-3°). (Found: C, 63.94; H, 4.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$: C, 64.07 ; H, 4.8%).

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